

LOCALIZED DAMAGE IN COMPOSITE STRUCTURES

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ABSTRACT

The effect of localized contact stresses and the resulting damage on the residual strength of composite laminates is addressed. The force-contact deformation, including damage effects is obtained from the solution of the contact problem between a thin laminate and a rigid spherical indenter. The damage region is estimated using a maximum fiber shear failure criterion and can be related to the compressive strength of the laminate. The residual strength predicted using the average stress failure criterion for an equivalent through crack, correlates well with experimental data reported in the literature.

Keywords: composites, indentation, contact law, damage, residual strength.

1. INTRODUCTION

Damage and subsequent strength loss in composite structures as a result of lateral impact or static loads is well known. Depending on the characteristics of the impact event, impactor mass, size, velocity, material and structural properties, impact damage is caused by either bending stresses and or either local contact stresses. The residual strength of composite structures can be reduced as much as 50% as a result of impact damage [1,2].

In References 1 and 2, a combined analytical and experimental study was conducted on the impact response of composite cylinders. For comparison reasons, the effect of impact energy on the residual strength of the cylinders is shown in Figure 1. It was found that damage in the empty cylinders was primarily caused by bending loads, whereas in the case of the cylinders reinforced with aluminum stiffeners, contact loads which were an order of magnitude higher, were the cause of the damage.

Recent work has been directed toward separating the local contact effects from the global structural response, such that results from static indentation laws may be used in analyzing the impact response [3,4]. The contact force-deformation relationship produced by a spherical indenter on a fiber-reinforced composite, has been shown to follow a Hertzian type contact law [5,6]. There are some uncertainties, however, when a Hertzian type contact analysis between a sphere and a half-

space is applied to thin laminates. During the initial stages of loading the Hertz contact law should be adequate, however, as higher loads cause extensive damage in the contact zone, the effects of damage should be a major factor in the response. Swanson and Resae [7] have conducted experiments where thin laminates resting on a rigid substrate were laterally loaded by a rigid spherical indenter. The data seem to follow the Hertzian contact law initially, but at higher loads softening associated with significant observed damage and permanent deformation is quite evident in the force-deformation response. Christoforou [8] predicted similar behavior by an analytical solution of the same problem.

The objective of this work is to address the effect of localized contact stresses and the resulting damage, on the residual tensile strength of fiber-reinforced composites. The damage zone is predicted using the analysis of Reference 8. By considering the weakening effect of the damage zone as an equivalent through crack, the residual strength is predicted using the average stress failure criterion [10,11]. The use of an effective crack as a model for the impact damage in fiber-reinforced composites has been considered previously [9,12], and appears to be useful. The analytical predictions correlate well with experimental data previously reported in the literature.

2. ANALYSIS

2.1. Contact Loading

The solution of the contact problem between a rigid sphere and a thin composite laminate resting on a rigid substrate, illustrated in Figure 2, has been presented in Reference 8. A brief description of the solution follows.

In contact problems where the contact radius is large compared to the thickness of the laminate ($a/h \gg 1$), the stresses may be assumed to be constant through the thickness. Thus, the governing differential equations for axisymmetric problems reduce to,

$$\frac{d\sigma_r}{dr} + \frac{\sigma_r - \sigma_\theta}{r} = 0 \quad (1)$$

The strains under the spherical indenter are expressed as,

$$\begin{aligned} \varepsilon_r &= \frac{du}{dr} \\ \varepsilon_\theta &= \frac{u}{r} \\ \varepsilon_z &= \frac{w}{h} = \frac{a^2}{2Rh} \left(1 - \frac{r^2}{a^2} \right) \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

where u and w are the radial and vertical displacements, respectively, h is the thickness of the laminate and R is the radius of the sphere. The vertical strain was obtained from the geometry of the deformation, and the indentation α at $r=0$ is given by

$$\alpha = w(0) = \frac{a^2}{2R} \quad (3)$$

In the elastic range, assuming transversely-isotropic material, the stresses in the laminate are obtained as,

$$\begin{aligned}\sigma_r &= \frac{\nu_{zr} E_r a^2}{4(1 - \nu_{rz} \nu_{zr}) Rh} \left(1 - \frac{r^2}{2a^2} \right) \\ \sigma_\theta &= \frac{\nu_{zr} E_r a^2}{4(1 - \nu_{rz} \nu_{zr}) Rh} \left(1 - \frac{3r^2}{2a^2} \right) \\ \sigma_z &= \frac{E_z a^2}{2(1 - \nu_{rz} \nu_{zr}) Rh} \left(1 - \frac{r^2}{a^2} \right)\end{aligned}\quad (4)$$

The contact force is obtained from the contact stress distribution as follows:

$$F(\alpha) = \int_0^a \sigma_z(r) (2\pi r) dr = \frac{\pi E_z a^2}{4(1 - \nu_{rz} \nu_{zr}) Rh} = \frac{\pi E_z R \alpha^2}{(1 - \nu_{rz} \nu_{zr}) h} \quad (5)$$

Damage effects are incorporated in the analysis by assuming the material to be perfectly plastic in the damage region and elastic elsewhere. Considering experimental evidence reported by Poe and Illg [9], which suggest fiber failure in shear for this type of loads, a maximum fiber shear failure criterion is applied to the largest normal stress.

$$\begin{aligned}(\sigma_z)_p &= 2S_f & r \leq b \\ (\sigma_z)_e &= \frac{E_z a^2}{2(1 - \nu_{rz} \nu_{zr}) Rh} \left(1 - \frac{r^2}{a^2} \right) & b \leq r \leq a\end{aligned}\quad (6)$$

where S_f is the fiber shear strength. At the interface $r=b$, and from Equation 6,

$$b^2 = a^2 - \frac{4Rh(1 - \nu_{rz} \nu_{zr}) S_f}{E_z} \quad (7)$$

By setting $b=0$ in Equation 10 the critical indentation for damage is obtained as,

$$\alpha_{cr} = \frac{2h(1 - \nu_{rz} \nu_{zr}) S_f}{E_z} \quad (8)$$

Finally, the total force can be obtained

$$F(\alpha) = \int_0^b 2S_f(2\pi r) dr + \int_b^a (\sigma_z)_e(2\pi r) dr = 2\pi S_f(2\alpha - \alpha_{cr}) \quad (9)$$

The contact force-deformation relationship of Equation 9 is valid when damage has been predicted to occur in the laminate.

2.2. Damage and Residual Strength

The radius of the damage zone in the laminate can be determined as a function of the applied contact load, by combining Equations 7,8 and 9.

$$b = \sqrt{\frac{F(\alpha)}{2\pi S_f} - R\alpha_{cr}} \quad (10)$$

The final step in the analysis is to estimate the loss of strength in the laminate from the damage zone predicted by the contact loading analysis.

Although several fracture models have been developed, not a single one is commonly accepted in the fracture of fiber-reinforced composites [13,14]. However, the Whitney-Nuismer average stress model [10], was found to predict well the notched strength of composite plates [14]. Also, Cantwell and Morton [12] applied the model in the assessment of the residual strength of impact-damaged fiber-reinforced epoxy. The average stress failure model is adapted here because it is also easy to use. By considering the weakening effect of the estimated damage zone as an equivalent through crack $2c=2b$, the residual strength of the laminate σ_r is predicted by

$$\frac{\sigma_r}{\sigma_0} = \sqrt{\frac{1-[c/(c+a_0)]}{1+[c/(c+a_0)]}} \quad (11)$$

where σ_0 is the un-notched strength and a_0 is the so called characteristic distance. This parameter was found to be not a material constant as previously thought, but rather laminate dependent. However, at least for a given material system and laminate configuration, it can be used as a constant which can be determined through a single test on one hole or crack size. This view is adapted here with good correlation to experimental evidence.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Calculations were carried out on a $[0/\pm 68/0]_S$ IM7/55A carbon/epoxy laminate and compared with experimental data reported in Reference 7. The fiber-reinforced coupons had a nominal thickness of 2.4 mm, were supported by a hardened steel block, and subjected to lateral static load by a hardened steel spherical indenter with a diameter of 15.88 mm.

Figure 3 shows the comparisons between analytical predictions and experimental data for the overall contact force-deformation response of the laminate. As can be seen damage has a dominant effect on the response and it is important that it is included in the analysis. The damage zone was predicted using a maximum fiber shear failure criterion. Since experimental data were not available for this material system, the fiber shear strength $S_f=310$ MPa [9] of AS4/55A, a similar Hercules carbon/epoxy system was used.

One important parameter in the analysis is the critical indentation α_{cr} given by Equation 8, at the onset of damage. The normalized critical indentation α_{cr}/h is in fact the critical normal strain ϵ_{cr} for damage to occur. This compressive strain may also be thought of as the maximum allowable strain for the laminate. By inserting all the necessary values in Equation 8, the calculated value of ϵ_{cr} was found to be -0.9%. This value is in agreement with experimental data [16,17] reporting similar compressive strengths for these composite material systems. A closer look of Equation 8 reveals a

simple stress-strain relationship in the normal direction and it is consistent with findings that fiber failures are best modeled by maximum stress or strain failure criteria. It is clear that indentation damage of composites is most sensitive to the shear strength of the fibers which is directly related to the compressive strength of the fibers. Thus, it is fair to conclude that indentation tests may provide an added opportunity for exploring the compressive strength of fiber composites. This is very important considering the difficulties associated with testing composites in compression. It should be kept in mind, however, that in order to provide these findings a solid foundation, more experimental work is needed.

Using Equation 10 the damage zone was predicted as a function of the contact force, as shown in Figure 4. By considering the weakening effect of the damage zone as an equivalent through crack the residual strength was predicted from Equation 11. The normalized residual strength as a function of the contact force is shown in Figure 5. As can be seen the correlation between the analytical predictions and the experimental data is encouraging. The characteristic distance a_0 used in Equation 11 was estimated to be 5.3 mm, by applying the average stress failure criterion to a through-hole specimen result reported in Reference 7. This value is consistent with the fact that this carbon/epoxy system was shown to exhibit higher failure strains than the earlier systems used to estimate the original value of 3.8 mm. Also experimental data for various composite material systems reported in [15], suggest a value for a_0 between 3.1 and 5.2 mm.

Finally, the simple analytical procedure for the localized damage assessment in composite laminates presented here is promising. The advantages of such models demonstrated here, is that they usually give significant insight for the problem in hand. A careful experimentalist may use these type of analyses to design experiments for static indentation laws, impact damage assessment and material characterization of fiber composites.

4. CONCLUSIONS

A simple analytical procedure has been presented for describing damage in thin composite laminates under localized contact loads. Damage was found to depend on the through the thickness properties of the laminate and the shear strength of the fibers. Ultimately the damage may be related to the compressive strength of the fibers, and thus, additional information on the stress-strain behavior of the material system in hand may be obtained. The residual strength under tensile loading was predicted using the average stress failure criterion and agrees well with experimental data reported in the literature.

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Fig. 1. Effect of the internal support and impact energy on the strength of carbon/epoxy cylinders [1].

Fig. 2. Geometry of the contact between a sphere and a thin laminate on a rigid substrate.

Fig. 3. Contact force-deformation for a thin supported laminate.

Fig. 4 Damage zone in thin, supported laminates under lateral contact loads.

Fig. 5 Effect of the contact force on the subsequent residual laminate tensile strength.